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Study of the Interrelationships between Musculoskeletal Disorders and Psychosocial Risk Factors in Occupational Health and Safety Technicians

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1 **Study of the Interrelationships between Musculoskeletal Disorders and**
2 **Psychosocial Risk Factors in Occupational Health and Safety**
3 **Technicians**

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13 Abstract

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15 Disorders (MSDs) and the exposure to psychosocial risk in a sample of 399
16 Occupational Health and Safety Technicians (OHSTs), deepening in the
17 associations between both aspects.

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24 situation of alert or emergency. It is highlighted that the fact of not feeling
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29 physical and psychosocial risk factors as well as the significant relationship
30 between these variables. Furthermore, the predictive model show the variables
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35 1. Introduction

36 Musculoskeletal Disorders (MSDs) account for one of the most frequent occupational
37 hazards internationally, being together with stress one of the leading causes of
38 temporary disability [1,2]. Approximately 7 out of 10 European workers report
39 suffering muscle discomfort on a regular basis, which they attribute to the postures and

40 efforts derived from the work they do [3]. Although there are no concrete figures, some
41 studies put the cost of MSDs for the health system at 2% of European Gross Domestic
42 Product [4].

43 In this context, the study of the risk factors that trigger MSDs has become, in the
44 last two decades, one of the main focuses of attention of research in the field of work
45 [5-7]. However, identifying such factors is a complex task because generally, multiple
46 risk factors are present in the same work environment [8]. In fact, although there are
47 several theoretical models that try to explain, from different approaches, the causative
48 agents of MSDs; [9] all of them recognize the convergence of various factors in the
49 process of generation of these disorders. Out of all these models, the biomechanical
50 approach [10] is currently the most used; focusing on aspects related to mechanical
51 overexposure due to excessive forces, high repetition, uncomfortable postures or
52 continued use of vibration tools and its effects on health.

53 At the same time, there is more empirical evidence that psychosocial risk factors
54 play an important role in the development of MSDs, and can predict their appearance
55 [11]. In this regard, there are numerous studies and meta-analysis carried out in the last
56 decade in different settings such as healthcare, in which numerous dis-ergonomic
57 factors converge (forced postures, repetitive movements, prolonged standing, manual
58 patient mobilization, etc.) and psychosocial risk (high intensity and workload,
59 relationship with patients, unbalanced expectations-results, etc.), which show the
60 connection between both variables.

61 For example, in the study by Dianat et al. [12] with a sample of 312 surgeons,
62 the associations between various psychosocial factors (such as work load and work
63 intensity) and the presence of discomfort in the knees, neck, lower back and shoulders
64 are highlighted. On the other hand, in the meta-analysis carried out by Bernal et al. [13]

65 the existence of relationships between high psychosocial demands and low control of
66 tasks with physical pain at the lumbar, knee and shoulder level is shown. Likewise,
67 effort-reward imbalance was associated with prevalent MSDs at any anatomical site and
68 low social support with incidental back pain. In Spain, Ballester and García [14]
69 reviewed 64 studies within this field, concluding that exposure to high demands, low
70 control over work, low social support, effort-reward imbalance, and inadequate work
71 organization are associated with discomfort and / or pain in upper extremities, neck,
72 lumbar back, lower extremities or in any body region.

73 On the other hand, the models of Schleifer, Ley and Spalding [15] and
74 Golubovich, Chang and Eatough [16] try to explain the contribution of psychosocial
75 risk factors to the development of MSDs. Firstly, relating exposure to stressors with
76 changes in breathing patterns and reduced blood flow, which end up affecting the tissue
77 and promoting the appearance of muscle injuries; and secondly, relating the perception
78 of stress situations with tensions that lead to muscle complaints. Another example is the
79 model proposed by Stock et al. [17] which includes, in addition to biomechanical and
80 personal aspects, six psychosocial variables that are interrelated with the appearance of
81 MSDs: intensity and time of work, emotional demands, autonomy, social support at
82 work, role conflict and job insecurity.

83 In short, it is becoming more evident that the physical and psychosocial **factors**
84 are aspects that are difficult to separate. Stress, excessive work load and demand, low
85 satisfaction, imbalance between the effort made and the reward received, time-related
86 pressure or little social support from bosses or colleagues, are key elements influencing
87 the discomfort and the frequency and intensity of physical symptoms, such as fatigue
88 and pain in the back, hands and wrist, increasing the incidence of MSDs [12,18-20].

89 Despite the foregoing, the absence of national and international studies that have
90 focused on the existence of possible associations between MSDs and psychosocial risk
91 factors among Occupational Health and Safety Technicians (OHSTs), who are part of
92 the External Prevention Service, and who are in charge of managing health and safety in
93 organizations, is observed. The activity of these professionals is divided into two work
94 scenarios, one developed in offices, with a high administrative workload, which takes
95 more than 50% of the working day; and the other, related to monitoring and preventive
96 training for client companies, which implies the concept of work in mobility [21]. Both
97 work scenarios have been modified in recent years by the intensification of ICT,
98 promoting the use of new electronic devices (smartphones, tablets, etc.) associated with
99 the spread of the so-called related emerging risks [22], such as the appearance of MSDs
100 and situations of psychosocial risk [23]. Therefore, the need to carry out research in this
101 field is evident, since prevention technicians are usually exposed to numerous
102 ergonomic risk factors, derived mainly from the continued use of Data Display Screens
103 and electronic devices [24,25], as well as psychosocial factors, related to the perception
104 of low prestige of the profession, excess of responsibility, lack of rewards, lack of
105 autonomy, lack of support from professional entities and the time pressure due to the
106 high workload [26], aspects that must be known for their evaluation and prevention.

107 **2. Objectives and Hypothesis**

108 The aim of this paper is to take a closer look into the associations between MSDs and
109 psychosocial risk factors in the OHST profession. Specifically, it is intended to answer
110 the following research questions:

- 111 1. Are there significant relationships between the prevalence of muscle ailments
112 and psychosocial risk factors?

113 2. What physical and psychosocial **factors** are able to explain the probability of
114 suffering from MDSs?

115 **3. Materials and Methods**

116 **3.1 Sample**

117 An incidental sample of a non-probabilistic type is used, consisting of 399 OHSTs
118 (47.6% men, 52.4% women) from different External Prevention Services (EPS) located
119 in Spain, with an average age of 40 years and, in half of the cases, with seniority longer
120 than 10 years. The selection of the sample was obtained through the Association of
121 External Prevention Services (AEPS), applying as exclusion criteria those technicians
122 with conditions of the musculoskeletal system or muscle ailments prior to their
123 incorporation to work as OHST. For this, a question was included in the questionnaire
124 in relation to this criterion.

125 As is known, the sample thus obtained does not allow it to be referred to, in the
126 strict sense, as statistically representative of all the technicians currently active, about
127 14000 currently, since its selection has been based on incidental criteria of convenience
128 and not randomized, a question that would have made data collection difficult. Despite
129 this, it can be stated that the group of participants constitutes a large group within the
130 population of interest to study and that allows an overview of the associations between
131 MSDs and the psychosocial risk factors considered.

132 **3.2 Questionnaire**

133 A descriptive and cross-sectional epidemiological study has been carried out, using two
134 questionnaires previously validated in the Spanish population.

135 To detect and analyze the existence of musculoskeletal symptoms, the
136 Standardized Nordic Questionnaire [27] is used, one of the most widely used methods
137 in the workplace for the pre-diagnosis of MSD [28]. The Questionnaire is made up of a
138 checklist of eleven items referring to the pain or discomfort perceived by workers in
139 different parts of the body, neck, shoulder, elbow, wrist and back; also, obtaining
140 information on the perception that workers have of the causes that are associated with
141 such discomfort.

142 On the other hand, for the evaluation of psychosocial risk factors, the Decore
143 Questionnaire [29] is used, since it shows adequate psychometrics properties [30] and
144 the main psychosocial factors susceptible to generate psychosocial risk in the OHST
145 profession: low control over the task, low organizational support, low rewards and high
146 cognitive demands [26]. All factors are interpreted based on four levels of exposure to
147 risk, (excellent, healthy, alert and emergency), except for the factor Cognitive Demands
148 (CD), which is interpreted based on three levels of increasing severity (alert-, healthy
149 and alert +). High scores in each factor indicates that the worker has an adverse
150 perception of psychosocial factors in their work environment. Furthermore, this
151 questionnaire also allows for obtaining a global vision of exposure to psychosocial risk
152 through the calculation of three indexes: Global Risk Index (GRI), Demand-Control
153 Imbalance Index (DCI) and Demand-Reward Imbalance Index (DRI).

154 To characterize the sample and establish study risk factors, a questionnaire
155 consisting of 28 self-constructed items was also used, which include, on one hand,
156 sociodemographic variables, such as age, gender, weight, height, etc. and, on the other
157 hand, different organizational aspects, such as level of training, seniority in the job,
158 work environments, use of electronic devices, etc.

159 **3.3 Procedure**

160 The questionnaire was created through a platform for online surveys, facilitating its
161 distribution and completion, it was sent to the Secretary of AEPS, who in turn,
162 forwarded it to the EPSs that are a part of the association. The online questionnaire was
163 sent from the EPSs to the OHSTs who work there, explaining the procedure and
164 objectives of the study in detail, and it could have been completed from any device.

165 The responses were recorded directly in the database linked to the questionnaire
166 without having access to any data that could identify the subject and preserving the total
167 anonymity of the respondents. Additionally, the first page of the platform contained the
168 informed consent of the participants.

169 The ethical principles underlying the research studies have been strictly
170 observed. In accordance with the ethical standards included in the 1979 Belmont Report
171 for the protection of human subjects participating in research, there are three general
172 ethical principles that should guide any research: autonomy, beneficence, and justice.

173 **3.4 Statistical Analysis**

174 Different descriptive analyses were carried out, providing the distribution of absolute
175 and relative frequencies for the qualitative variables and measurements of position and
176 dispersion in the case of quantitative variables.

177 To study the association between a multiple response variable with a single
178 response variable, the χ^2 test was used; while the relationships between two qualitative
179 variables were examined using χ^2 test and Fisher's test. On the other hand, to analyze
180 the existence of differences in means, the Student's t test was used for two independent
181 samples; while the comparison between three or more groups was carried out with the
182 ANOVA and Kruskal-Wallis tests.

183 To predict the appearance of musculoskeletal complaints, a multivariate binary
184 logistic model was constructed. In addition, a logistic regression model was performed
185 to calculate predictions, constructing the associated nomogram, which represents the
186 predicted probability of experiencing discomfort based on specific values of the
187 explanatory variables. For the calculation of the GRI and DCI, linear models were built
188 given the continuous nature of these variables.

189 For the construction of the nomogram, the Regression Modeling Strategies
190 (RMS) and DynNom packages were used [31,32].

191 Statistical analyses were performed using the R program (R Development Core
192 Team), version 3.4.4.

193 **4. Results**

194 *4.1 Descriptive analysis*

195 In the analysis of the prevalence of muscle ailments, it was taken into account that 7.8%
196 of the surveyed technicians had congenital muscle pathologies or prior to the
197 development of their professional activity, for which they were excluded from the
198 study.

199 Regarding organizational variables, most of the participants consider that they
200 have an adequate level of training; however, with regard to emerging risks, about 46.6%
201 of those sampled thinks that they do not have enough knowledge. Regarding the
202 distribution of working time, although most of it takes place in the office, approximately
203 one third of the working day involves activities outside of the office and about 37% of
204 those surveyed affirm that they work outside working hours. In this context, the
205 computer is the most used electronic device, followed by the smartphone, with an
206 average use time of 16.5 hours per week. Tables 1 and 2 show the main values obtained.

207

[Table 1 and 2 here]

208 Regarding the analysis of the presence of musculoskeletal symptoms, 77.17% of
209 the participants claimed to have suffered some ailment. Specifically, the parts of the
210 body most affected in the last twelve months are the neck (46.5%), dorsolumbar area
211 (32.3%), right shoulder (22.8%) and wrist (20.9%). This trend, although with lower
212 percentages, is repeated when asking about ailments in the last seven days (Figure 1). In
213 addition, 21.47% of those surveyed present neck and dorsolumbar ailments
214 simultaneously.

215

[Figure 1 here]

216 Regarding the analysis of psychosocial **factors**, as shown in Figure 2, the two
217 most critical aspects are, on the one hand, those related to the rewards that the worker
218 obtains for their work, with 54.7% of the technicians in a situation of alert or
219 emergency, and on the other hand, with the demands and cognitive requirements of the
220 tasks, with 38.8% in a state of alert +. However, a high percentage of the sample scores
221 positively in the social support factor, with 79.6% being those who are in a healthy or
222 excellent level.

223

[Figure 2 here]

224 Conversely, 45.3% of OHSTs are exposed to an alert or emergency GRI.
225 Regarding the DCI and DRI indexes, high percentages of technicians in a state of alert
226 or emergency are also obtained (53.4% - DRI, 40.8% - DCI), which represents a very
227 high percentage of workers who are in a psychosocially adverse situation (Figure 3).

228

[Figure 3 here]

229 ***4.2 Correlational analysis***

230 The study of the existing associations between the variables studied shows, on one

231 hand, the existence of positive and significant relationships between the prevalence of
232 muscular ailments, gender, weekly hours of office work and training in emerging risks.
233 As can be seen in Table 3, 83.78% of women present muscular ailments, while in men it
234 decreases to 70.29%. Regarding to working time, it is observed that technicians who
235 suffer discomfort spend more hours working in the office than those who do not.
236 On the other hand, 83.61% of the technicians, who consider that they do not have
237 sufficient training in emerging risks, present discomfort. This percentage decreases to
238 66.18% in those workers who perceive they are well trained.

239 *[Table 3 here]*

240 In fact, when considering only neck ailments, similar results were found to the
241 previous ones, evidencing the existence of significant associations with gender, office
242 work hours and taking breaks from work. This last aspect acquires special relevance,
243 since the percentage of technicians who present discomfort goes from 48.22% in those
244 who take breaks to 81.25% in those who do not (data not shown).

245 Regarding the psychosocial field, significant relationships were found between
246 the GRI index and training in emerging risks, feeling professionally valued, working
247 outside working hours, taking breaks from work, and perceived health (Table 4). The
248 same relationships were found in the DCI and DRI indices (data not shown).

249 Again, training in emerging risks acquires special relevance, so that technicians
250 who think they are not well trained are more exposed to psychosocial risk. On the other
251 hand, people who work outside working hours are more exposed to psychosocial risk
252 than those who do not, as well as those who do not have the option of taking breaks
253 throughout their work day, reaching in this case emergency exposure levels ($GRI > 70$).

254 *[Table 4 here]*

279 It was found that the variables that best predict the probability of suffering from
280 discomfort are gender, training in emerging risks, perceived health and exposure to
281 psychosocial risk. Specifically, the results show that the probability of suffering
282 muscular discomfort in the case of women is twice (OR = 2.067) that of the case in
283 men. In the same way, people who perceive they do not have adequate training in
284 emerging risks also double the probability of suffering from musculoskeletal discomfort
285 (OR = 2.231) compared to those who do perceive adequate training. From a
286 psychosocial point of view, having higher scores on the GRI increases the probability of
287 suffering from muscle discomfort (OR = 1.019). Lastly, those professionals who
288 perceive a bad or regular state of health are much more exposed to suffering discomfort
289 than those who perceive it as very good (OR = 8.907).

290 Regarding the data obtained through the models related to exposure to
291 psychosocial risk (Table 7), it is highlighted that the fact of not feeling professionally
292 valued, working outside working hours, having musculoskeletal discomfort and
293 perceiving a state of poor or fair health, increase the GRI score. The variables that show
294 a more pronounced significant increase in the three indices studied (GRI, DCI, DRI) are
295 the perception of lack of professional assessment, perception of poor or fair health,
296 prevalence of musculoskeletal ailments and working outside working hours.

297 *[Table 7 here]*

298 The increase that these variables imply in the mean values of the psychosocial
299 risk indices gives rise to a change in their diagnosis (see Table 5), going from being in a
300 healthy state to an alert state (scores higher than 50 points). Not feeling professionally
301 valued would go on to represent a state of emergency in DRI (DRI > 71) and very close
302 to emergency in GRI (≥ 71) and DCI (≥ 64). On the contrary, taking breaks is
303 postulated as an important modulator of both global psychosocial risks and the

304 imbalance demands control by decreasing the values of both indexes, GRI (-16.0) and
305 DCI (-18.4), a decrease that represents a valuation of the DCI index excellent (≤ 36).

306 Starting from the data obtained with the aforementioned logistic regression
307 models, the associated nomogram was constructed (Figure 4), within 75% accuracy
308 (Area Under the Curve for model, AUC= 0.747; 95% CI 0.673, 0.821), and the
309 sensitivity and specificity were 0.971 and 0.286, respectively. The nomogram
310 represents the probability predicted by a logit model of suffering discomfort from
311 specific values of the explanatory variables gender, age, training in emerging risks,
312 health perceived risk and exposure to psychosocial risk through GRI values.

313 For example, taking as a reference a 40-year-old working woman, with a good
314 perception of her health, adequate training in emerging risks and exposed to a level of
315 psychosocial risk of alert (GRI = 60 points), the predicted probability of suffering
316 MSDs is around 86%. In case of maintaining all the variables, but with a healthy
317 psychosocial risk level (GRI = 40 points), the probability would decrease by around
318 80% and if instead of a woman it were a man it would decrease even more, to 66%.

319 A dynamic version of the nomogram is provided at the following URL:

320 <https://unir.shinyapps.io/nomogram/>

321 *[Figure 4 here]*

322 **5. Discussion**

323 The results show, in line with previous studies [3] that a very high percentage of
324 workers have muscle ailments (77.17%), the neck being the most affected part of the
325 body, with 46.5% of people with ailments in the last 12 months, followed by the
326 dorsolumbar area, shoulder and wrist.

327 The main factors that present a significant relationship with the prevalence of
328 these ailments are gender, training received in emerging risks and working hours. In the
329 case of neck discomfort, the lack of breaks throughout the working day is particularly
330 relevant. The latter is an important factor, if we pay attention to the forced postures
331 associated with the use of Visual Display Terminals (VDTs). These factors are common
332 to those observed in other studies, in which the main working tool are the VDTs, as in
333 the case of OHSTs [33-35]

334 Regarding exposure to psychosocial risk factors, there are a high number of
335 workers who are in a situation of alert or emergency, both from a global perspective of
336 psychosocial risk (45.3%), and attending to the demand-control imbalance (40.8%) and
337 demand-reward (53.4%). Again, the lack of training and the absence of breaks are
338 presented as factors related to situations of high demand for work and under control and
339 reward, to which are added working outside working hours and a negative self-
340 perception in relation to health and professional valuation at work.

341 The foregoing highlights the high exposure of OHSTs to both physical and
342 psychosocial risk factors, which in turn increases the probability of developing MSDs,
343 results that are consistent with those obtained in studies carried out on other sectors,
344 [36,37]. On the other hand, our results show a significant positive association between
345 the presence of MSDs and the three psychosocial risk indices considered, in line with
346 the results found in previous studies [11,38-40]. Various studies show the interactive
347 effects of this double exposure on the etiology of work-related MSDs. For example,
348 Devereux et al. [41,42] establishes that the impact of exposure to physical and
349 psychosocial risks in the generation of MSDs has a stronger effect than exposure to
350 physical or psychosocial factors individually. Also [43], observed that the imbalance of
351 effort and reward allows predicting discomfort in the upper extremities, in workers who

352 use VDTs for more than 20 hours per week. On the other hand, there is evidence
353 indicating that MSDs of the shoulders and neck are largely associated with exposure to
354 psychosocial work hazards, whereas MSDs of the lower back, elbows, wrists and hands
355 are better explained based on exposure to ergonomic work hazards [44].

356 This type of association has been observed in some studies, although the latest
357 related reviews indicate that the studies that exist to date are not conclusive when it
358 comes to establishing whether the association is causal [44-46], which would be in line
359 with our findings: the presence of discomfort represents a significant increase in the risk
360 index scores. However, the multivariate model indicates that higher scores on the GRI
361 hardly increase the probability of suffering muscle discomfort (OR = 1.019), somewhat
362 lower than that obtained in other studies (OR = 1.15-1.66) [18].

363 The multivariate model showed other interesting results. On the one hand,
364 women are twice as likely to suffer from musculoskeletal symptoms, in line with
365 previous research, with odds ratios ranging from 1.8 to 2.27 [7,35]. The higher risk of
366 MSD symptoms among female workers might be attributed to both biological
367 differences as well as differences in social roles, activities, and behaviours [36]. At the
368 same time, the fact of not receiving specific training in emerging risks is significantly
369 associated with the probability of suffering from musculoskeletal discomfort, doubling
370 the possibility of having symptoms in those workers who perceive they are not
371 sufficiently trained [7,47,48].

372 Finally, the perception of health is another of the variables that shows to have
373 more impact both on the probability of suffering from musculoskeletal discomfort, and
374 on the perception of exposure to psychosocial risk. Specifically, those OHTSs that
375 perceive a poor or regular state of health multiply the probability of suffering from
376 musculoskeletal discomfort by almost nine, and markedly increases the values of the

377 global risk indices, going on to represent much more unfavourable situations compared
378 to the perception of psychosocial risk. The results are consistent with other studies that
379 show this relationship [49].

380 The construction of the nomogram based on the results obtained, allows for a
381 quick visualization based on the different related factors and how the probability of
382 suffering discomfort varies. However, these values must be taken with caution as well
383 as taking into account the limitations presented by these tools. Another limitation of this
384 study that should be highlighted is the incidental nature of the sample, as well as those
385 associated with the limitations of the techniques used, such as the use of a questionnaire
386 to collect data in relation to the presence of MSDs is a subjective metric, which may be
387 biased depending on the knowledge of the respondent about the terms used. Also, the
388 instruments for measuring psychological constructs are often subjective and rely on
389 personal reflections [11].

390 Finally, it should be pointed out that the development of effective strategies to
391 prevent and effectively manage the possible appearance of work-related MSDs is based
392 on the need to understand the multifactorial nature of their etiological development [50].
393 Furthermore, there is evidence to suggest that interventions with a focus on work
394 organization problems have the potential to reduce work stress and, in turn, neck and
395 upper extremity symptoms [44,51,52].

396 In short, the findings of the present study have shown the relationship between
397 exposure to psychosocial and physical risks and the presence of different MSDs, that
398 increases the need to assess both aspects jointly. Specifically, gender, lack of training
399 and breaks, negative self-perception in relation to health and professional assessment at
400 work, and high psychosocial risk were key aspects in explaining the probability of
401 suffering from MSDs.

402 **Conflict of Interest**

403 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest associated with this publication
404 and they will not provide access to the study data. All authors contributed equally to the
405 conception and design of the research, to the analysis of the data, and to the writing of
406 the final version of the manuscript.

407 **Compliance with Ethical Standards**

408 All procedures performed in studies involving human participants were in accordance
409 with the ethical standards of the institutional and/or national research committee and
410 with the 1964 Helsinki declaration, the 1979 Belmont Report, and its later amendments
411 or comparable ethical standards.

412 **References**

- 413 [1] European Agency for Safety and Health at Work (EU-OHSA). Work-related
414 musculoskeletal disorders: prevalence, costs and demographics in the EU.
415 Luxembourg: EU-OSHA; 2019.
- 416 [2] Vos T, Barber RM, Bell B, et al. Global, regional, and national incidence,
417 prevalence, and years lived with disability for 301 acute and chronic diseases and
418 injuries in 188 countries, 1990–2013: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of
419 Disease Study 2013. *Lancet*. 2015;386(9995):743-800.
- 420 [3] European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions
421 (Eurofound). Sixth European Working Conditions Survey – Overview report (2017
422 update). Luxembourg: Eurofound; 2017. (European Working Conditions Survey
423 2015; EF1634).
- 424 [4] Bevan S. Economic impact of musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) on work in
425 Europe. *Best Pract Res Clin*. 2015;29(3):356-373.
- 426 [5] Dianat I, Karimi MA. Musculoskeletal symptoms among handicraft workers
427 engaged in hand sewing tasks. *J Occup Health*. 2016;58(6):644-652.
- 428 [6] Coenen P, van der Molen HF, Burdorf A, et al. Associations of screen work with
429 neck and upper extremity symptoms: a systematic review with meta-analysis. *Occup
430 Environ Med*. 2019;76(7):502-509.
- 431 [7] López-González MJ, González S, González-Menéndez E. Prevalence of
432 musculoskeletal problems in laboratory technicians. *Int J Occup Saf Ergon*. 2019
433 Sep 3:1-12. Spanish.
- 434 [8] Bugajska J, Zołnierczyk-Zreda D, Jedryka-Goral A, et al. Psychological factors at
435 work and musculoskeletal disorders: a one year prospective study. *Rheumatol Int*.
436 2013;33(12):2975-2983.
- 437 [9] Márquez M. Modelos teóricos de la causalidad de los trastornos
438 musculoesqueléticos [Theoretical models of the causality of musculoskeletal
439 disorders]. *Ingeniería Industrial. Actualidad y Nuevas Tendencias*. 2015;4(14):85-
440 102. Spanish.
- 441 [10] Van der Beek A, Frigs-Dresen M. Assessment of mechanical exposure in
442 ergonomic epidemiology. *Occup Environ Med*. 1998;55(5):219-299.

- 443 [11] Tang, KHD. A review of psychosocial models for the development of
444 musculoskeletal disorders and common psychosocial instruments. *Arch. Curr. Res.*
445 *Int.* 2020;20(7):9-19.
- 446 [12] Dianat I, Bazazan A, Souraki MA, et al. Work-related physical, psychosocial
447 and individual factors associated with musculoskeletal symptoms among surgeons:
448 implications for ergonomic intervention. *Appl Ergon.* 2018 Feb;67:115-124.
- 449 [13] Bernal D, Campos-Serna J, Tobias A, et al. Work-related psychosocial risk
450 factors and musculoskeletal disorders in hospital nurses and nursing aides: a
451 systematic review and meta-analysis. *Int J Nurs Stud.* 2015;52(2):635-648.
- 452 [14] Ballester AR, García AM. Asociación entre la exposición laboral a factores
453 psicosociales y la existencia de trastornos musculoesqueléticos en personal de
454 enfermería: revisión sistemática y meta-análisis [Occupational exposure to
455 psychosocial factors and the existence of musculoskeletal disorders in nursing staff:
456 a review of studies and meta-analysis]. *Rev Esp Salud Pública.* 2017
457 Apr;7:91:e201704028. Spanish.
- 458 [15] Schleifer L, Ley R, Spalding T. A hyperventilation theory of job stress and
459 musculoskeletal disorders. *Am J Ind Med.* 2002;41(5):420-432.
- 460 [16] Golubovich J, Chang CH, Eatough EM. Safety climate, hardiness, and
461 musculoskeletal complaints: a mediated moderation model. *Appl Ergon.*
462 2014;45(3):757-766.
- 463 [17] Stock S, Nicolakakis N, Messing K, et al. What is the relationship between
464 work-related musculoskeletal disorders and psychosocial workplace factors? [Quelle
465 est la relation entre les troubles musculo-squelettiques (TMS) liés au travail et les
466 facteurs psychosociaux?] *Perspectives interdisciplinaires sur le travail et la santé.*
467 2013;15(2):1-12. French.
- 468 [18] Eatough EM, Way JD, Chang C. Understanding the link between psychosocial
469 work stressors and work-related musculoskeletal complaints. *Appl Ergon.*
470 2012;43(3):554-563.
- 471 [19] Lang J, Ochsmann E, Kraus, T, et al. Psychosocial work stressors as
472 antecedents of musculoskeletal problems: a systematic review and meta-analysis of
473 stability-adjusted longitudinal studies. *Soc Sci Med.* 2012;75(7):1163-1174.
- 474 [20] Widanarko B, Legg S, Devereux J, et al. The combined effect of physical,
475 psychosocial/organizational and/or environmental risk factors on the presence of

476 work-related musculoskeletal symptoms and its consequences. *Appl Ergon.*
477 2014;45(6):1610–1621.

478 [21] Messenger JC, Gschwind L. Three generations of telework: new ICTs and the
479 (R) evolution from home office to virtual office. *New Technol Work Employ.*
480 2016;31(3):195-208.

481 [22] Brocal F, Sebastián MA, González C. Theoretical framework for the new and
482 emerging occupational risk modeling and its monitoring through technology
483 lifecycle of industrial processes. *Saf Sci.* 2017 Nov;99:178-186.

484 [23] González-Menéndez E, López-González MJ, González Menéndez S, et al.
485 Principales consecuencias para la salud derivadas del uso continuado de nuevos
486 dispositivos electrónicos con PVD [Major health consequences a rising from the
487 continued use of new electronic devices with visual display units]. *Rev Esp Salud*
488 *Pública.* 2019 Sep;93:e1-11. Spanish.

489 [24] So CB, Cheng SA, Szeto PG. Cumulative IT use is associated with
490 psychosocial stress factors and musculoskeletal symptoms. *Int J Environ Res Public*
491 *Health.* 2017;14(12):1541.

492 [25] Waersted M, Hanvold TN, Veiersted KB. Computer work and musculoskeletal
493 disorders of the neck and upper extremity: a systematic review. *BMC Musculoskelet*
494 *Disord.* 2010 Apr;11: 79-94.

495 [26] Sánchez-Herrera IS, Bestratén M, Orrit, J, et al. 1ª Encuesta en España a
496 Técnicos de Prevención de Riesgos Laborales [1st Survey in Spain of Occupational
497 Health and Safety Technicians]. Madrid: AEPSAL and Instituto Nacional de
498 Seguridad e Higiene en el Trabajo (INSHT); 2017. Spanish.

499 [27] Kuorinka I, Jonsson B, Kilbom A, et al. Standardised Nordic questionnaires for
500 the analysis of musculoskeletal symptoms. *Appl Ergon.* 1987;18(3):233-237.

501 [28] Fogleman M, Lewis RJ. Factors associated with self-reported musculoskeletal
502 discomfort in video display terminal (VDT) users. *Int J Ind Ergon.* 2002;29(6):311-
503 318.

504 [29] Luceño L, Martín J, Díaz EM, et al. Un instrumento de evaluación de riesgos
505 psicosociales en el entorno laboral "el Cuestionario Decore" [An instrument for
506 assessing psychosocial risks in the workplace: the Decore questionnaire].
507 *EduPsykhé: J Psychol Psychopedagogic.* 2008;7(2):131-153. Spanish.

- 508 [30] Luceño L, Martín J, Rubio, S, et al. Análisis factorial confirmatorio del
509 cuestionario DECORE [Confirmatory factor analysis of the DECORE
510 questionnaire]. *Ansiedad y Estrés*. 2010;16(2):237-248. Spanish.
- 511 [31] Harrell JR. Regression modeling strategies [Cran-r Project web site]. Version
512 5.1-3. Viena: The R Foundation for Statistical Computing; 2019.
- 513 [32] Jalali A, Roshan D, Alvarez-Iglesias A, et al. Visualizing statistical models
514 using dynamic nomograms [Cran-r Project web site]. Version 5.0.1. Viena: The R
515 Foundation for Statistical Computing; 2019.
- 516 [33] Griffiths KL, Mackey MG, Adamson BJ. The impact of a computerized work
517 environment on professional occupational groups and behavioural and physiological
518 risk factors for musculoskeletal symptoms: a literature review. *J Occup Rehabil*.
519 2007;17(4):743-765.
- 520 [34] Johnston V, Souvlis T, Jimmieson, NL, et al. Associations between individual
521 and workplace risk factors for self-reported neck pain and disability among female
522 office workers. *Appl Ergon*. 2008;39(2):171-182.
- 523 [35] Tornqvist EW, Hagberg M, Hagman, M, et al. The influence of working
524 conditions and individual factors on the incidence of neck and upper limb symptoms
525 among professional computer users. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health*.
526 2009;82(6):689-702.
- 527 [36] Nodooshan S, Rastipisheh P, Yadegarfar G, et al. The effect of work-related
528 psychosocial stressors on musculoskeletal disorder symptoms in hospital attendants.
529 *Work*. 2020;67(2):477-486.
- 530 [37] Zulkarnain MA, Setyaningsih Y, Wahyuni I. Personal characteristic,
531 occupational, work environment and psychosocial stressor factors of
532 musculoskeletal disorders (MSDs) complaints on bus driver: literature review. Paper
533 presented at International Conference on Environment, Sustainability Issues, and
534 Community Development; 2021 Jan 21 October; Semarang, Indonesia.
- 535 [38] Burgel BJ, White MC, Gillen M, et al. Psychosocial work factors and shoulder
536 pain in hotel room cleaners. *Am J Ind Med*. 2010;53(7):743-756.
- 537 [39] De Jonge J, Bosma H, Peter R, et al. Job strain, effort-reward imbalance and
538 employee well-being: a large-scale cross-sectional study. *Soc Sci Med*.
539 2000;50(9):1317-1327.

- 540 [40] Lee SJ, Lee JH, Gillen M, et al. Job stress and work- related musculoskeletal
541 symptoms among intensive care unit nurses: a comparison between job demand-
542 control and effort- reward imbalance models. *Am J Ind Med.* 2014;57(2):214-221.
- 543 [41] Devereux JJ, Vlachonikolis IG, Buckle, PW. Epidemiological study to
544 investigate potential interaction between physical and psychosocial factors at work
545 that may increase the risk of symptoms of musculoskeletal disorder of the neck and
546 upper limb. *Occup Environ Med.* 2002;59(4):269-277.
- 547 [42] Devereux J, Rydstedt L, Kelly V, et al. The role of stress and psychological
548 factors in the development of musculoskeletal disorders: the stress and MSD study.
549 Sudbury: Health and Safety Executive; 2004. (Report 273).
- 550 [43] Krause N, Burgel B, Rempel D. Effort-reward imbalance and one-year change
551 in neck-shoulder and upper-extremity pain among call center computer operators.
552 *Scand J Work Environ Health.* 2010;36(1):42-53.
- 553 [44] Liu HC, Cheng Y, Ho JJ. Associations of ergonomic and psychosocial work
554 hazards with musculoskeletal disorders of specific body parts: a study of general
555 employees in Taiwan. *Int. J. Ind. Ergon.* 2020 Mar;76:102935.
- 556 [45] Hauke A, Flintrop J, Brun E, et al. The impact of work-related psychosocial
557 stressors on the onset of musculoskeletal disorders in specific body regions: a
558 review and meta-analysis of 54 longitudinal studies. *Work Stress.* 2011;25(3):243-
559 256.
- 560 [46] Koch P, Schablon A, Latza U, et al. Musculoskeletal pain and effort-reward
561 imbalance-a systematic review. *BMC Public Health.* 2014 Jan;14:37.
- 562 [47] Pedersen MT, Andersen CH, Zebis MK, et al. Implementation of specific
563 strength training among industrial laboratory technicians: Long-term effects on
564 back, neck and upper extremity pain. *BMC Musculoskelet Disord.* 2013 Oct;14:287-
565 298.
- 566 [48] Shuai J, Yue P, Li L, et al. Assessing the effects of an educational program for
567 the prevention of work-related musculoskeletal disorders among school teachers.
568 *BMC Public Health.* 2014 Nov;14:1211.
- 569 [49] Holmgren K, Dahlin-Ivanoff S, Björkelund C, et al. The prevalence of work-
570 related stress, and its association with self-perceived health and sick-leave, in a
571 population of employed Swedish women. *BMC Public Health.* 2009 Mar;9:73.

- 572 [50] Östergren PO, Hanson BS, Balogh, I, et al. Incidence of shoulder and neck pain
573 in a working population: effect modification between mechanical and psychosocial
574 exposures at work? Results from a one year follow up of the Malmö shoulder and
575 neck study cohort. *J Epidemiol Community Health*. 2005;59(9):721-728.
- 576 [51] Bongers PP, Ijmker S, van den Heuvel S, et al. Epidemiology of work related
577 neck and upper limb problems: psychosocial and personal risk factors (part I) and
578 effective interventions from a bio behavioral perspective (part II). *J Occup Rehabil*.
579 2006;16(3):279-302.
- 580 [52] Macdonald W, Oakman J. Requirements for more effective prevention of work-
581 related musculoskeletal disorders. *BMC Musculoskelet Disord*. 2015 Oct;16:1-9.
582

583 **Figures**

584 Figure 1. Presence of ailments in different parts of the body in the last: twelve months
585 (gray bar) and seven days (black bar). **Note: MSDs = musculoskeletal disorders.**

586 Figure 2. Analysis of the level of exposure for each psychosocial factor: cognitive
587 demands: (□) healthy, (□) alert - and (■) alert +. Control, organizational support and
588 rewards: (■) excellent, (□) healthy, (■) alert and (■) emergency. **Note: OHSTs =**
589 **occupational health and safety technicians.**

590 Figure 3. Exposure level analysis for each global psychosocial risk index: (■) excellent,
591 (□) healthy, (■) alert and (■) emergency. **Note: DCI = demand-control imbalance index;**
592 **DRI = demand-reward imbalance index; GRI = global risk index; OHSTs =**
593 **occupational health and safety technicians.**

594 Figure 4. Predictive nomogram of musculoskeletal complaints. **Note: MSDs =**
595 **musculoskeletal disorders.**

596 **Tables**

597 Table 1. Socio-demographic and occupational characteristics of **occupational health and**
598 **safety technicians.**

599 Table 2. Quantitative socio-demographic and occupational characteristics of
600 **occupational health and safety technicians.**

601 Table 3. Associations between socio-demographic and occupational variables and
602 reported musculoskeletal symptoms among the participants (N = 399).

603 Table 4. Associations between studied variables and psychosocial risk among the
604 participants.

605 Table 5. Associations between reported musculoskeletal symptoms and psychosocial
606 risk variables among the participants.

607 Table 6. Multivariate analysis for musculoskeletal symptoms (simplified model).

608 Table 7. Multivariate analysis for psychosocial risk (simplified model).

Table 1. Socio-demographic and occupational characteristics of occupational health and safety technicians.

Variable	%	Variable	%
Gender		Overtime work	
Male	52.4	Yes	36.7
Female	47.6	No	63.3
Physical exercise		Work brakes	
Yes	69.9	Yes	93.8
No	30.1	No	6.2
Muscular ailments		Feel professionally valued	
Congenital or previous		Disagree	19.42
Yes	7.80	Undecided	20.71
No	92.20	Agree	59.87
Emerging risks training		Perceived health	
Agree	24.3	Moderate or poor	17.91
Undecided	29.1	Good	69.55
Disagree	46.6	Very good	12.54

Table 2. Quantitative socio-demographic and occupational characteristics of occupational health and safety technicians.

Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	P0	P25	P50	P75	P100
Age	40.22	8.33	24.00	34.00	41.00	46.00	64.00
BMI	25.71	5.66	14.69	22.64	24.86	22.78	76.86
Work experience	9.52	6.80	0.00	3.00	10.00	15.00	38.00
Computer w.h.	23.10	13.54	0.00	16.00	25.00	34.00	40.00
Laptop w.h.	11.97	13.90	0.00	0.00	6.00	20.00	40.00
Smartphone w.h.	16.54	13.66	0.00	5.00	11.00	27.00	40.00
Office w.h.	23.98	9.53	0.00	20.00	24.00	30.00	40.00
Out of office w.h.	14.51	8.67	0.00	10.00	15.00	20.00	40.00
Home w.h.	4.60	6.81	0.00	0.00	2.00	6.00	40.00

Note: BMI = body mass index; **P = percentile**; w.h. = working hours per week.

Table 3. Associations between socio-demographic and occupational variables and reported musculoskeletal symptoms among the participants (N = 399).

Variable	Musculoskeletal symptoms				p				
	Yes		No						
	%		%						
Gender					0.007				
Male	70.29		29.71						
Female	83.78		16.22						
Emerging risks training					0.023				
Disagree	83.61		16.39						
Undecided	75.31		24.69						
Agree	66.18		33.82						
	Yes		No						
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	P25	P75	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	P25	P75	p
Office w.h.	24.39	9.11	20	30	21.63	10.79	15.25	29.75	0.046

Note: **P = percentile**; w.h. = working hours per week.

Table 4. Associations between studied variables and psychosocial risk among the participants.

Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	GRI		<i>p</i>
			P25	P75	
Emerging risks training					0.027
Disagree	52.12	21.29	36.50	64.00	
Undecided	43.14	19.67	30.00	56.00	
Agree	44.11	22.26	29.50	57.00	
Overtime work					<0.001
No	42.80	18.93	31.50	57.00	
Yes	55.84	23.23	37.00	71.75	
Work brakes					<0.001
No	71.33	19.33	61.25	87.25	
Yes	46.00	20.73	32.00	59.00	
Feel professionally valued					<0.001
Disagree	67.13	18.70	57.75	82.00	
Undecided	52.48	17.13	40.75	81.00	
Agree	39.81	18.58	28.00	52.00	
Perceived health					<0.001
Moderate or poor	62.57	19.11	50.00	77.25	
Good	45.54	19.72	32.00	59.00	
Very good	38.49	22.17	25.50	48.50	
Musculoskeletal symptoms					<0.001
No	38.86	20.26	25.00	52.00	
Yes	49.66	21.18	35.00	62.00	

Note: **GRI = global risk index; P = percentile.**

Table 5. Associations between reported musculoskeletal symptoms and psychosocial risk variables among the participants.

Variable	Musculoskeletal Symptoms								<i>p</i>
	Yes				No				
	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	P25	P75	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	P25	P75	
Demands	67.59	15.74	58.00	80.00	60.58	15.43	53.00	69.00	0.002
Control	40.61	17.71	28.00	53.00	37.63	16.57	24.00	47.00	0.228
Rewards	53.67	20.72	41.00	69.00	43.12	23.21	27.00	60.00	0.001
Support	38.03	18.50	24.00	49.00	31.82	18.22	17.00	40.00	0.018
GRI	49.66	21.18	35.00	62.00	38.86	20.26	25.00	52.00	<0.001
DCI	47.95	19.62	35.00	60.00	39.49	17.97	28.00	48.00	0.002
DRI	54.55	21.22	39.00	69.00	41.85	21.02	30.00	54.00	<0.001

Note: DCI = demand-control imbalance index; DRI = demand-reward imbalance index; GRI = global risk index; P =percentile.

Table 6. Multivariate analysis for musculoskeletal symptoms (simplified model)

Risk Factor	General Symptoms		
	OR	95% CI	<i>p</i>
Age	0.963	[0.927, 1.001]	0.055
Psychosocial risk	1.019	[1.003, 1.037]	0.022
Gender			
Female	2.067	[1.090, 4.009]	0.028
Emerging risk training			
Disagree	2.231	[1.033, 4.857]	0.041
Undecided	1.195	[0.537, 2.653]	0.660
Perceived health			
Moderate or poor	8.907	[2.526, 37.912]	0.001
Good	4.569	[2.041, 10.418]	<0.001

Note: CI = confidence interval; OR = odds ratio; Reference for emerging risk training = agree; gender = male; perceived health = very good.

Table 7. Multivariate analysis for psychosocial risk (simplified model)

Risk Factor	GRI		DCI		DRI	
	Coef.	<i>p</i>	Coef.	<i>p</i>	Coef.	<i>p</i>
Overtime work						
Yes	9.073	<0.001	8.452	<0.001	11.324	<0.001
Work brakes						
Yes	-16.020	<0.001	-18.419	<0.001	-8.265	0.058
Feel professionally valued						
Disagree	22.677	<0.001	16.867	<0.001	24.400	<0.001
Undecided	12.378	<0.001	7.803	0.002	13.616	<0.001
Musculoskeletal symptoms						
Yes	6.003	0.020	5.483	0.027	7.886	0.002
Perceived health						
Moderate or poor	10.072	0.016	7.107	0.074	9.864	0.016
Good	0.905	0.778	0.343	0.910	0.470	0.882

Note: Coef. = value that increases or decreases the index; DCI = demand-control imbalance index; DRI = demand-reward imbalance index; GRI = global risk index; Reference for feel professionally valued = agree; overtime work, work brakes and musculoskeletal symptoms = no; perceived health = very good.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

